

CONCEPT OF ILLEGAL MIGRATION AND ITS CRIMINAL-LEGAL SIGNIFICANCE

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ANNOTATION

In the article, the essence of illegal migration is revealed from a criminal-legal point of view. All signs and elements belonging to the term are summarized within a single concept. The definitions given by several scientists to the concept of illegal migration have been studied. The terms “illegal migration”, “unlawful migration” and “criminal migration” are different from each other. From the above definitions of illegal migration, there are several ways to become an illegal migrant. All opinions were analyzed and a proposed definition of illegal migration was developed.

Key words: illegal migration, unlawful migration, criminal migration, socio-economic, political, legal and national-demographic factors, foreign citizens, stateless persons, illegal migrant.

It is known that, as each problem has its own characteristics, there are certain aspects that reveal the essence of illegal migration, and it is important for law enforcement officers to understand the issues related to illegal migration. Because, from the point of view of Criminal law, determining the legal content of the concept, first of all, implies the generalization of all signs and elements related to this phrase within a single concept. This makes it possible to distinguish a certain concept from other phenomena and categories that are close and similar to it [1].

Thus, today in the legal literature there is no consensus on the concept of illegal migration, as well as terminological inconsistency regarding the analyzed term. In particular, one group of authors uses the term “illegal migration” to explain the issue under analysis, others call it “unlawful migration”, and the third group of authors uses the term “criminal migration”.

In this matter, the most frequently used term by the authors is “illegal migration”. In particular, A.N. Shkilev, who has studied this problem, defines the concept of illegal migration as follows: “Illegal migration is the territorial movement of the population in physical space, under the influence of socio-economic, political, legal and national-demographic factors, in violation of the

current rules of international law and the requirements of the national legislation” [17]. In addition, E.Kh.Kakhbulaeva writes that “illegal migration is a rapidly developing socially dangerous phenomenon that violates the current international law and national legislation and threatens national security and the interests of the entire international community” [8]. However, in our opinion, the content of illegal migration is not fully revealed in these definitions, for instance, they do not specify the issues related to the subjects of illegal migration and do not reveal the aspects related to its objective signs.

Continuing the reasoning of scientists, G.E.Dudin and S.V.Kalinins note the following: “... Illegal migration in the general sense means any movement in the territory of the state in violation of the legal requirements that determine the procedure for entering the country and being in its territory” [5]. However, in our opinion, this definition is given in a rather narrow sense, in which, along with the shortcomings mentioned above, the content of illegal migration is limited to taking into account only the cross-border features of movement.

Along with the above scientists A.Fedorako states as follows “... illegal migration is the activity that occurs as a result of the movement of foreign citizens and stateless persons in violation of the established order of entry, transit, stay and exit on the territory of a specific country” [16]. In addition, T.B.Smashnikova rightly interprets the concept of “illegal migration” in her own way, that is, she points: “...illegal migration is an act of migration on the territory of the state in order to change the temporary place of residence or place of residence of the population is voluntary or forced migration across state borders in violation of the requirements of the law” [13].

In addition, A.V.Sukharnikova, who studied this problem, notes that a person must have the following characteristics to be considered an illegal migrant: 1) crossing the border of a foreign country bypassing the designated control points; 2) living on the territory of the state in violation of the rules of the current national migration legislation; 3) it is necessary to understand the persons who entered the country by illegal means or obtained residence permit documents” [14]. However, in our opinion, the definitions designated by A.Fedorako, T.B.Smashnikova and A.V.Sukharnikova in relation to the issue under discussion also have some shortcomings and do not fully reveal the meaning of illegal migration, for instance, they limit the migration from one country to another by violating national law of receiving country, they do not take into account the types of migration and their specific characteristics, in addition, the authors state only illegal crossing of the border of the receiving country is the basis for illegal

migration. In our opinion, the content of illegal migration should also include situations related to the violation of the requirements of international law, and its types and content should also be taken into account, and of course, as one of the reasons for illegal migration, it should not be connected only with the crossing of the state border, the reason for which is the migrant's entry into the country. On the other hand, legally crossing the orders of the receiving country (for instance, entering the country with a tourist visa) can be considered as illegal migration, but the subsequent stay in the country or the activities carried out by the migrant may be illegal (expired visa, performing labor activities in violation of migration legislation, etc.).

It can be seen from the above-mentioned points that the issue has not been approached in depth. Because, in the legal literature, there is a completely different approach to this issue, there are also separate scientific studies, in particular, in this regard, M.N.Akhmedov states that illegal migration by citizens of this country, foreign citizens or stateless persons in the national legislation of the host country is a violation of the established rules on entry, exit, stay and transit [3]. Meantime, according to A.M. Iskhakov, illegal migration means the activity that a foreign citizen or a stateless person moves within the country in accordance with national legislation or international law rules, as well as regardless of the purpose and duration of arrival, to carry out labor activities, enter, leave, stay in the country, and cross the country's territory in violation of the established transit procedure [7].

A.N. Jerebtsov understands illegal migration as "...the movement of individuals in violation of the established legal regimes and legal procedures for migration, for instance violation of the established order of migration rules" (*in case of violation of internal (socio-economic) movement of migration rules – citizens of the country and in case of violation of established migration rules related to movement from the territory of a foreign state to the territory of the country or from the territory of the country to the territory of a foreign state –foreign citizens (stateless persons)*) [6].

E.S.Krasinets, E.S.Kubishin, E.V.Tyuryukanova define illegal migration as follows: concept of "illegal migrant" includes those who illegally entered the state territory (crossed the border from unmarked places with unauthentic or forged documents or without any documents), includes persons who are in the territory of the country illegally (who have not properly issued documents for their stay in the country) and persons engaged in illegal economic activities [10]. Here we should note that we do not support the view of illegal migrants as the main sign

that they are engaged in “illegal economic activity” proposed by these authors. Because, in our opinion, it would be wrong to include the implementation of any economic activity by foreign citizens and stateless persons (migrants) in the content of the studied definition. These crimes are not directly related to migration law, so they should not be taken into account when determining the legal or illegal status of a migrant. In our opinion, the procedure for conducting business or other economic (commercial) activities depends not on the regime of stay in the country, but on the rules of stay in the country. We believe that the definition of illegal migration should include not only foreign citizens or stateless persons, but also all persons participating in these processes.

In addition, according to N.R.Asmandiyarova, illegal migration means the illegal entry of foreign citizens or stateless persons into the territory of the country or the illegal exit of foreign citizens, stateless persons and citizens of the country from this country, as well as foreign citizens or illegal stay (residence) of stateless persons in the territory of the country or illegal transit of foreign citizens or stateless persons through the territory of the country [2].

Based on the above, it can be said that most authors believe that illegal migration can occur only in cases of crossing the state border. However, the views of N.R. Asmandiyarova, A.N. Jerebtsova and M.N. Akhmedov deny this opinion, according to their notes, an illegal migrant can also be in the case of internal migration. In this case, a citizen of the country violated the internal movement of migration rules can be good example. This approach is also supported by A.N.Shkilev, that is, he considers the possibility of illegal migration to exist not only when crossing state borders, but also in any territorial movement of the population in physical space. Such views are, of course, more or less noteworthy, and support for these views is possible.

However, in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the expression “migration” [lat. migratio – migration (of the population) from one place to another] means relocation of the population from one place to another within the country or from one country to another country” [15]. In particular, internal migration, like external migration, can be carried out in violation of the law. An example of this is the offense specified in Article 223 of the Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan (violation of the rules of the Passport system). Thus, this rule imposes punishment for living of a citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan without a passport or identification ID card or with an invalid passport or identification ID card, without registration of permanent residence or temporary residence, as well as a foreign citizen permanently

residing in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan and a stateless person living with an ID card (residence certificate in the Republic of Uzbekistan) without registration of permanent residence or temporary residence will result in a fine of two to three times the base calculation amount. So, logically, not only external but also internal migration can be illegal if the violation of the legislation in a certain area is caused by giving this or that phrase the meaning of “illegal”.

From the point of view of the problem we are considering, it is important to pay attention to another aspect, because, as we mentioned above, some authors applied the term “illegal” to name the problem under consideration. For instance, L.L.Rybakovsky uses the term “illegal migration” in his works. In his opinion, “... illegal migrants are those who illegally crossed the state border or crossed the border legally, but later violated the procedure established by the law regarding their stay in the country (for instance, not registering their place of residence or migration register, or the period of stay in the country has expired and etc.) [12].

Meantime, M.A.Magerramov stated that illegal migration is defined as violation of the rules of entry, stay, exit and transit by a foreign citizen or stateless person from the territory of a foreign state [11].

According to V.A.Volokh, illegal immigration means the entry and stay of a foreign citizen in this country in violation of the requirements of the current legislation of the country, which determines the procedure for entering, staying, and transiting the country, and arbitrary detention of the foreign citizen during his stay on the territory of the country of entry. Here, it is necessary to understand that this changes its legal status»[4].

As we have seen, from the definitions of illegal migration given by L.L.Rybakovsky, M.A.Magerramov and V.A.Volokh, it is possible to say that they have the same definition of illegal migration and unlawful migration.

As we have already mentioned, another term used for illegal migrants is “foreign migration”. According to P.N.Kobets, criminal migration is a real, practical, and plausible threat to the purpose of human learning and the development of criminal technologies. In addition, T.B.Smashnikova notes “...criminal migration is the voluntary or forced crossing of the state or its administrative borders by the population with the purpose of knowingly and illegally entering the territory of the receiving state in order to carry out criminal activities prohibited by the rules of criminal law and within the scope of its influence.

Meantime, these definitions are noteworthy in that the authors show that criminal migration is manifested not only in the crossing of state borders, but also in any territorial movement of the population. Based on this, it can be said that

criminal migration can be external (crossing state borders) and internal (without crossing state borders). However, in our opinion, criminal migration is a separate phenomenon that requires a separate scientific study, since its main purpose is to commit a crime. Criminal migration is a very dangerous type of migration, which does not belong to the type of illegal migration and cannot be included in its concept, because criminal migration is a more dangerous social phenomenon than illegal migration.

In short, from the above definition of illegal migration, it is possible to distinguish several ways of becoming an illegal migrant: 1) crossing the state border without the necessary documents (without a visa, passport, etc.); 2) violation of the intended purpose of coming to the receiving country (entering the country with a tourist visa, getting a job, etc.); 3) violation of the established regime of stay in a certain place (for instance, failure to register for temporary residence or migration, expiration of the specified period of stay in the territory of the country (expired visa, expired permit for temporary residence in the territory of the country, expired period of residence in the country); 4) in a certain area movement; 5) subjects of illegal migration can be foreign citizens, stateless persons and citizens of Uzbekistan who participated in the organization of this process; 6) an integral element of illegal migration is the violation of the internal legislation of the countries or international rules that regulate the sphere of entry and exit, stay, transit, and employment.

Based on the above, we consider it appropriate to define illegal migration as follows, i.e. illegal migration is the entry of foreign citizens or stateless persons into the Republic of Uzbekistan in violation of the established procedure, living with invalid documents, registration at the place of temporary stay, uncomplying with the established procedure of moving or choosing a place of residence, not leaving the country after the end of the stay, uncomplying with the rules of transit through the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, violating the procedure for attracting and using foreign labor in the country by authorized organizations and employers, as well as the legislation on migration, as well as sending citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan abroad illegally or organizing employment abroad. It is understandable, such activities are carried out by persons who do not have the appropriate authority

Иқтибослар/Сноски/References:

- 1.Отажонов А. А. Legal analysis of signs participation in the crime // Право и жизнь. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 62.
- 2.Асмандиярова Н.Р. Борьба с незаконной миграцией на региональном уровне: уголовно-правовой и криминологический аспекты: по материалам

- Республики Башкортостан. Автореф. дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. – М., 2008. – С. 8.
- 3.Ахмедов М.Н. Противодействие нелегальной миграции: уголовно-правовой и криминологический аспекты. Автореф. дис. ... канд.юрид.наук. – М., 2016. – С. 8.
- 4.Волох В.А. Формирование и реализация государственной миграционной политики Российской Федерации: состояние, тенденции, пути реализации». Автореф... дис. д-ра полит. наук. – М., 2013. – С.22.
- 5.Дудин Г.Е., Калинина С.В. Операция «Нелегальный мигрант» // Миграционное право. – 2013. – №2. – С. 24-29.
- 6.Жеребцов А.Н. Административно-правовой статус незаконных мигрантов в Российской Федерации нуждается в законодательном закреплении. // Общество и право. – 2009. – № 2. – С.241.
- 7.Исхаков А.М. Уголовно-правовые и криминологические аспекты организации незаконной миграции. Автореф. дис. ... канд.юрид.наук. – Казань, 2018. – С. 8-13.
- 8.Кахбулаева Э.Х. Уголовно-правовые и криминологические аспекты организации незаконной миграции. Автореф. дис ... канд. юрид. наук. – Ростов-на-Дону, 2011. – С. 14.
- 9.Кобец П.Н. Организация деятельности правоохранительных органов Российской Федерации в сфере борьбы с преступностью иностранных граждан и лиц без гражданства // Вести. Вост.-Сиб. института МВД России (научно-практический журнал). – 2003. – № 3 (26). – С.28.
- 10.Красинец Е. С., Кубишин Е. С., Тюрюканова Е.В. Нелегальная миграция в Россию. – М., 2000. – С.29.
- 11.Магеррамов М.А. Нелегальная миграция: понятие, общественная опасность, уголовно-правовое и криминологическое противодействие: по материалам России и Азербайджана. Автореф. дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. – Ростов-на-Дону, 2008. – С. 8.
- 12.Рыбаковский Л.Л. Практическая демография. [Электрон манба] URL: <http://rybakovsky.ru/migracia2.html>
- 13.Смашникова Т.Б. Административно-правовое противодействие незаконной миграции в Российской Федерации и республике Беларусь: сравнительно-правовой анализ. Автореферат дисс. ... канд. юрид. наук. – Челябинск. 2012. – С.9.

14. Сухарникова А.В. Незаконная миграция и миграционный контроль в России // Административное право и административный процесс в России. – 2013. – № 2. – С. 36

15. Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати: 8000 дан ортиқ сўз ва сўз бирикмаси. Ж. П. Е-М / Таҳрир ҳайъати: Т. Мирзаев (раҳбар) ва бошқ.; ЎзР ФА Тил ва адабиёт ин-ти. – Тошкент. «Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси» Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2006. – Б. 588-589.

16. Федорако А. Миграция населения: понятие, причины, последствия. // Журнал международного права и международных отношений. – 2012. – № 4. – С.6.

17. Шкилев А.Н. Миграция: уголовно-правовые и криминологические аспекты. Автореферат дисс. ... канд. юрид. наук. – Нижний Новгород, 2006. – С.12.

